

Paper 7
**ROLE OF ON-LINE TUTORING IN THE INDIAN
SCENARIO**

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Abstract:

India is a country where education practices are at their best. Indian parents want to impart quality education to their children irrespective of where they live. Most of the Indians who migrate to foreign countries for lucrative jobs want to give the best education to their wards. This is where online tutoring comes to existence. Over the last few years, online tutoring from India for students across the globe has taken on the contours of an industry. Online tutoring is a big segment in parallel education, which is expected to grow in a rapid pace. Indian e-tutoring companies reach out to the students across the globe. Online tutoring is the best job that can lure Indian women who would like to become a good homemaker without sacrificing her career. Online tutoring is conducted by companies who hire tutors, who are available on demand. Thus, online tutoring from India plays a vital role which is driven by availability of large pool of talented teachers at lower costs. This paper highlights the working mode of on-line tutoring in the context of Indian women who find it difficult to juggle between home and office. The paper also focuses on the impact of online tutoring in the Indian market. This paper also does a comparative study of a few online tutoring companies to analyze their growth. This paper highlights the future of e-learning in the Indian context.

Keywords: online tutoring, e-learning, e-tutoring companies, on-line learning

Introduction:

Students from primary classes to Class XII are now actively leveraging websites and apps in their search for excellent tutors. In the last few years, the approach of the parent, teacher, and student fraternity in India has been veering towards the online world, especially in urban and semi-urban India. A handful of startups rode high on this behavioral change and succeeded in the online tutoring domain. Online tutoring is not just about connecting teachers and students. It should have the ability to map coaching to respective curriculum and syllabus. To succeed, the companies need to have a good tutor management platform, robust training, remote monitoring of tutors, and tools and techniques using analytics and artificial intelligence(AI) to ensure an

effective outcome for each student[1]. But preserving the retention rate of students and minimizing the attrition rate of tutors will define the growth and sustainability of a company in this domain.

A teacher is a trained professional who teaches a group of students. Teachers' pay rates vary considerably depending on the grade level that is being taught, the level of education that the teacher has, which state they reside in and whether the position is full-time or part-time[2]. When you work as an employee, you don't have to invest any money up front or find your own clients, but your pay rate, work hours, and how you work will be more restricted. A tutor, on the other hand, is an informal professional who gives individuals additional or remedial instruction in a given subject[3]. While you need to have extensive knowledge of a subject, you don't need any specialized training to be a tutor. When a woman works as a tutor, she can be hired on as an employee, independent contractor, or can choose to open up your own home-based tutoring business. When you set up your own business, you have more flexibility with scheduling, choosing clients, and setting your rates, but you'll also have to find your own customers, set up your business, and pay self-employment taxes. Establishing a tutoring business is easy and has relatively low start-up costs. Some items you'll need to get started are a phone line or Smartphone, a computer, high-speed internet access, a printer and scanner, and a website to market your business.

The demand for online tutoring from India is driven by its large talent pool of teachers and lower costs. This is similar to the demand for the well-established Indian software and services and business process outsourcing industries. Then there is the advantage of sheer convenience. In most of these companies, online tutors are available 24 hours a day for one-on-one help. Students can log in at their convenience and assignments can be discussed through online chat sessions and voice. A virtual whiteboard allows the use of charts, graphs and diagrams.

Impact of online tutoring on Indian economy:

Over the last few years, online tutoring from India for students across the globe has taken on the contours of an industry. Along with other services in the burgeoning person-to-person off-shoring (PPO) space, it has tremendous growth potential: In the U.S. market alone, revenues for Indian tutoring companies are estimated by some to be at \$20 million today, and industry players expect the total to reach \$2 billion in three to five years [5].

While there are no firm numbers about the industry's size, estimates suggest that well over 100 players fill the space. They range in size from the venture-fund backed TutorVista.com, which has 600 tutors and 10,000 students, to Tutors Worldwide India, a fully-owned subsidiary of the U.S. Company Socratic Learning, with 250 tutors [6]. There are also mom-and-pop outfits with five tutors or fewer. Science, mathematics and English are usually taught. Offerings include homework help, regular grade tutoring, and preparation for the SAT, ACT and other exams. In many cases, tutors work from their homes. Though prices vary, they are much lower than those at U.S. tutoring firms, in some cases as low as \$10 an hour. TutorVista.com, which charges \$99.99 per month for unlimited tutoring, aims to make its service part of a family's monthly budget, like a health club membership.

A recent research puts online tutoring from India as one of the PPO services to watch out for. Others with strong growth potential are website development, graphic design, and editorial and writing services [7]. According to the research, the growth of the Internet, small offices, home businesses and individuals depends on the technological advancements and they can as well utilize PPO services. Individually taken, each contract is often of low value, usually between \$100 and \$5,000. Since the number of end consumers and small businesses is enormous, the total addressable market in the United States alone easily exceeds \$20 billion. Indian e-tutoring companies haven't forayed only into the United States [8]. They are also reaching out to students in the United Kingdom, Canada, Australia, China and West Asia. But it is the U.S. online tutoring market, currently estimated at \$200 million and which some players say represents more than half the global market. TutorVista, for instance, has students in 13 countries, but more than 90% of its revenues come from the United States.

Business models in online tutoring:

Indian companies who are already in the education business and start-ups have been quick to spot these opportunities and are trying out different business models. Some companies, like Educomp Solutions and TransTutors, have tied up with U.S. e-tutoring firms and get work subcontracted from them[9]. As the back-end vendors for the U.S. firms, these Indian companies put up the infrastructure and hire and train tutors in India. In most cases, the course content is provided by the U.S. Company, which also performs the marketing, brand building and student acquisition.

Another business model that companies, including TutorVista, have adopted is the direct-to-consumer route [10]. Along with the back-end operations, these companies develop course content and reach out to students directly. Some companies, such as Career Launcher, started their e-tutoring operations as back-end providers, learned the ropes, and then branched out to the retail segment [11]. Others are keeping both options open, a strategy they obviously prefer to keep under wraps for fear of upsetting their U.S. partners.

Each of these business models has its own opportunities and challenges. While the subcontracting model has a low gestation period, it is also very competitive. With an eye toward getting the work, Indian companies tend to undercut each other. The result is low margins, around 10% [12]. On the other hand, the direct-to-consumer model offers much higher margins, around 25% to 30% [13]. But it requires large up-front investments for brand building and customer acquisition.

Conclusion:

In this paper, the primary differences between tutor and teacher along with their pros and cons have been highlighted. The paper also reflects the economic growth of online tutoring in the Indian business scenario. The paper throws light on the different business models in online tutoring along with their opportunities and challenges. Some examples of online business companies and their growth in the Indian market have been discussed. To sum up, online tutoring helps individuals, especially women to devote their time to work as well as to their domestic affairs. Online tutoring helps to boost the country's economy by outsourcing our talent

to all over the world. The future of online tutoring seems to be very promising for both the tutors as well as the learners’.

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